

Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters using Phosphorus Pentoxide. Part II. Coumarins from Polyhydric Phenols and α -Naphthol.

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In an earlier part of this work (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129) it has been shown that resorcinol reacts with ethyl acetoacetates to form a coumarin and not a chromone even in presence of phosphorus pentoxide, which favours chromone formation (Petscheck and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2015; Simonis and Lehmann, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 697; Simonis and Remmert, *ibid.*, p. 2229).

The condensation of polyhydric phenols, *e.g.* orcinol, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol and also of α -naphthol with ethyl acetoacetates using phosphorus pentoxide has been studied in this work and the products obtained in these cases are also coumarins and not chromones. These phenols also condense most readily in the cold with much rise of temperature with ethyl acetoacetates in presence of phosphorus pentoxide and the condensation products are in all cases identical with the coumarins, prepared using sulphuric acid according to Pechmann's method, as is proved by their mixed melting points and also by the identity of their derivatives.

It is interesting to observe that orcinol condenses with the ethyl acetoacetates in presence of sulphuric acid to form products, which are soluble in alkali without any fluorescence unlike the 7-hydroxycoumarins and hence they are probably 5-hydroxycoumarins as was shown by Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1646).

The causes of the coumarin and chromone formation in these condensations are being investigated and the results of the condensation of monohydric phenols with β -ketonic esters using phosphorus pentoxide will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumarins from Orcinol.

5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin (β Methylhomoumbelliferone).
Phosphorus pentoxide (18 g.) is gradually added to a mixture of

orcinol (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) cooled in ice. Vigorous reaction sets in in the cold with much evolution of heat. When the reaction ceases, the cold mass is treated with water and the solid is washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 248°; the melting point is not depressed when mixed with a specimen of the coumarin prepared by Pechmann and Cohen's method (*Ber.*, 1881, 17, 2187) using sulphuric acid.

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 195°. (The acetyl derivative of Pechmann and Cohen's coumarin also melts at 195°).

5-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4:7-dimethylcoumarin is prepared by adding phosphorus pentoxide in the cold to a solution of orcinol and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate in a few c.c. of alcohol. The cold mass is poured into water and the pasty solid is dissolved in cold caustic alkali, the alkaline solution extracted with ether and the aqueous solution acidified. The precipitate is washed with a solution of sodium bicarbonate and crystallised from rectified spirit in felted needles, m.p. 295°. The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from alcohol in long needles, m.p. 160°. It is identical with the compound prepared using sulphuric acid by Pechmann and Hanke (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 354).

5-Hydroxy-3:4:7-trimethylcoumarin, prepared in a similar manner from orcinol and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (in alcohol), is isolated and purified as usual. Two products are obtained; one, is soluble in alkali with blue fluorescence and the other dissolves in alkali without any fluorescence. The non-fluorescent product is isolated on repeated fractional crystallisation from alcohol as cubes, m.p. 250°. (Found: C, 70.44; H, 5.93. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88 per cent.). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallises from alcohol in needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 68.20; H, 5.61. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent.). The identical compound (m.p. 250°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 135°) is also obtained with sulphuric acid, there being no depression of the melting point when mixed with the other specimen.

5-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-4:7-dimethylcoumarin is prepared from orcinol and ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate and sulphuric acid. It crystallises from dilute alcohol or glacial acetic acid in needles, m.p. 206°. (Found: C, 71.48; H, 6.31. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.2 per cent.).

The interaction of orcinol and ethyl α -ethyl (or α -propyl or α -isopropyl) acetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide leads to

two products in each case, both soluble in alkali, one with blue fluorescence and the other without any fluorescence and they could not be satisfactorily separated.

Coumarins from Pyrogallol.

7:8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (β -*Methylpaphnetin*) is prepared by adding, in the cold, phosphorus pentoxide (18 g.) to a mixture of pyrogallol (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.). It crystallises from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 235° , the melting point not being depressed when mixed with a sample of β -methylpaphnetin prepared by Pechmann and Duisberg (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119) with sulphuric acid.

7:8-Dihydroxy-3-chloro-4 methylcoumarin is obtained by adding phosphorus pentoxide to a solution of pyrogallol and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate in a few c.c. of alcohol. It crystallises from alcohol in lustrous needles, m.p. 265° . The *acetyl* derivative crystallises in prisms from alcohol, m.p. 197° . It is identical with the 3-chloro-4-methylpaphnetin prepared by using sulphuric acid by Pechmann and Hanke (*loc. cit.*) ; no depression of the melting point is observed when the two are mixed.

7:8-Dihydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin is prepared by condensing pyrogallol and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate using phosphorus pentoxide and finally heating for half an hour on the boiling water-bath. It is obtained as cubes (m.p. 270°) from glacial acetic acid. The yield is very poor in this case. The identical compound is obtained by using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. The mixed melting point of the compounds is also 270° . (Found: C, 64.13; H, 4.92. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.85 per cent.).

7:8-Dihydroxy-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin is obtained by adding, in the cold, sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) to a mixture of pyrogallol (5 g.) and ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate (5 g.) and keeping the solution overnight. It crystallises from dilute alcohol as lustrous rhombic plates, m.p. 218° . (Found: C, 65.38; H, 5.52. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.45; H, 5.45 per cent.).

It has not been possible to condense pyrogallol with ethyl α -ethyl- (or α -isopropyl-) acetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide even at a higher temperature.

Coumarins from Phloroglucinol.

5:7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, *5:7-dihydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin* and *5:7-dihydroxy-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin* have been prepared by the condensation of phloroglucinol with ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl α -methylacetoacetate and ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate respectively in presence of phosphorus pentoxide but the experimental details are not given as they have already been described by Canter, Curd and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, p. 1255). It has been observed by the author that the addition of a little absolute alcohol is much advantageous.

5:7-Dihydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin, prepared by adding phosphorus pentoxide in the cold to phloroglucinol and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate dissolved in a little alcohol, is crystallised in needles from acetic acid. It melts with decomposition at 306-308°, the m.p. not being depressed when mixed with the coumarin, prepared with sulphuric acid by Dey's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1648).

Coumarins from α -Naphthol.

4-Methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone is prepared by adding phosphorus pentoxide in the cold to a solution of α -naphthol and ethyl acetoacetate in a little alcohol. The product obtained on pouring the mass into water, is dissolved in boiling absolute alcohol (charcoal) from which on cooling beautiful needles melting at 167° separate. The mixed melting point of this compound and the coumarin prepared by Bartsch (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1966) is also 167°.

3-Chloro-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone is obtained by the interaction of α -naphthol, ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide. The product crystallises from glacial acetic acid, melts at 225-27° and is identical with the compound described by Dey (*loc. cit.*) there being no depression of the m.p.

3:4-Dimethyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone, obtained by the condensation of α -naphthol and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate using phosphorus pentoxide, crystallises in shining needles from glacial acetic acid and melts at 197-99°. (Found: C, 80.42; H, 5.44. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80.35; H, 5.35 per cent.). The identical compound melting at 197-99° is also obtained by condensing α -naphthol, ethyl α -methylacetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid. The mixed melting point is also 197-99°.

3-Propyl-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone is prepared by the interaction of α -naphthol and ethyl α -propylacetoacetate using sulphuric acid. It crystallises in needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 118°. (Found: C, 80.88; H, 6.41. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.95; H, 6.35 per cent.). No definite product could be isolated by using phosphorus pentoxide.

3-isoPropyl-4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone is obtained from α -naphthol and ethyl α -isopropylacetoacetate using sulphuric acid in the usual manner. It crystallises in needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 80.99; H, 6.21. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.95; H, 6.35 per cent.). No definite product has been isolated by using phosphorus pentoxide.

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